

CERTIFICATION OF STRUCTURAL COMPOSITE COMPONENTS USED ON THE MD900 HELICOPTER

Stuart E. Dutton¹, R. A. (Dick) Lofland²

¹*Cooperative Research Centre for Advanced Composite Structures Ltd
361 Milperra Road, Bankstown, NSW, Australia, 2200*

²*McDonnell Douglas Helicopter Systems, 5000 E. McDowell Rd, Mesa AZ 85215-9797*

SUMMARY: This paper will discuss the application of structural composites used on the McDonnell Douglas (MD900) Explorer Helicopter. It will concentrate on Hawker deHavilland's part in the selection, qualification, and certification of composites materials used on the helicopter. It will also discuss the design and manufacturing concepts and some of the manufacturing processes used to achieve the light weight and high performance characteristics of this machine.

KEYWORDS: FAA certification, material selection and qualification, composite structural testing, and composite manufacturing.

INTRODUCTION

The MD900 Explorer helicopter is the first new versatile rotorcraft of the 21st century. The eight place, twin-engine MD Explorer is the safest, quietest helicopter in its class. The helicopter features the composite NOTAR (No Tail Rotor) anti-torque system, bearingless all-composite rotor system, and many applications of composites in the fuselage.

HDH INVOLVEMENT IN THE MD EXPLORER

Hawker deHavilland Ltd. (HDH) began its involvement with McDonnell Douglas Helicopter System (MDHS) in the McDonnell Douglas (MD) Explorer program in 1988 when it became the first of several off-shore US companies to participate in the collaboration.

Originally, the brief was to design and manufacture the fuselage, tailboom and empennage structures. However, later the effort was scaled down slightly and MDHS retook responsibility for the boom and tail.

A very challenging target for vehicle empty weight was issued and it was apparent from the outset that novel structures would be required to meet these performance goals.

The cooperative arrangement was that MDHS would, as applicant for Certification, retain design responsibility but that HDH would carry out the detail design to MDHS approved procedures. External loading was included in the detail design specification provided by MDHS.

In order to minimize certification and maintenance costs, it was agreed that a common system of materials would be used. This was particularly significant with respect to the composites selected. A common set of (composite) materials meant that testing could be shared and data pooled between the two companies.

FUSELAGE STRUCTURE

The MD Explorer fuselage shown in Figure 1 is a hybrid with carbon fiber epoxy composite selected for the external body shells and some internal structure such as floors, keels and fuel cell support structure. Aluminum alloy is used for the supporting framework of the shell and also on the transmission deck. These choices were made for the following reasons:

- The external shape was highly curved.
- The internal structure had many interfaces with systems under the design control of MDHS which were expected to be subjected to a high rate of change through the design process.
- The deck temperatures were too high for the composite material systems that were under consideration.
- Issues of survivability in the event of a crash landing dictated a metal frame to support the machinery above the cabin area.

The consequence of the first was that components, particularly in the cockpit area, were of extremely complex shape and presented design and manufacturing challenges. The door pillar for instance is a hollow section created by bonding two Z section moldings together with adhesive in a secondary operation. The final assembly has a developed length of around 8.2 feet or 2.5 meters and has severe twists and bends along its length. The mating halves need to match closely if the bonding is to be successful. This has presented significant challenges in the tool design and manufacture.

Secondary bonding is used in the construction of all the cockpit details and in some of the remaining shell structure. Early production models had tub shell assemblies that involved a secondary bonding operation for the longerons and a tertiary bonding operation for installation of the fuel cell support ribs. Later versions dropped the latter processes in favor of mechanical fasteners (blind rivets) which are also used to attach the composite shell to the aluminum substructure.

The composite structure was of both stiffened (solid) laminate and honeycomb cored design. Much of the stiffened laminate was designed in the highly post-buckled range with buckling ratios up to seven in some locations.

ROTOR SYSTEM

The rotor composite components shown in Figure 2 consist of five main rotor blades which utilize S-2 Glass/Epoxy, E-Glass/Epoxy, Nomex Honeycomb Core, Titanium and Nickel (abrasion strips) and Stainless Steel (bushings). The blades are manufactured in components using filament winding and hand lay-up, they are inspected and then co-bonded. The root end bushings are then secondarily bonded and then machined. The abrasion strips and trim tabs are then secondarily bonded.

The five flexbeams are manufactured using S-2 Glass/Epoxy, E-Glass/Epoxy and Stainless Steel Bushings. The processes are filament winding and hand lay-up. They are then assembled in a closed mold and co-cured. After trim and inspection some secondary bonding takes place.

The five pitchcases are made from IM-7 Carbon/Epoxy, 8 Harness Broadgoods/Epoxy and Titanium and Stainless Steel. The parts are manufactured on a split mandrel using filament winding and hand lay-up. They are then placed in a closed mold internally pressurized and autoclave cured.

Figure 2

MD 900 EXPLORER

EMPTY WEIGHT	3238 LBS.
COMPOSITE WT.	18.9 PERCENT
STRUCTURAL WT.	1425 LBS.
COMPOSITE WT.	43 PERCENT

Figure 1

CERTIFICATION APPROACH

The certification basis was FAR 27 with AC20-107 (A) providing guidance in particular for the certification of the composite materials.

While composite rotor blades are quite common, the MD 900 is the first US certified helicopter to extensively employ composite materials in primary airframe structure. Specification documents for these new materials, and the processes for their fabrication were issued by MDHS after development with the HDH team.

The certification of materials, and components followed the now established “Building Block” approach, i.e. Materials and Process Qualification (coupon testing), Designallowables (coupon testing), Verification of Allowables (details testing), Sub-component and Full Scale Testing.

The design was certified by analysis and verified by test. This relies on using analyses to establish the critical loading cases and minimum margins of safety and by performing tests to establish (a) the accuracy of loading (Flight Testing) and (b) the adequacy of structural modeling and conformation of the failure modes (Structural Testing). An additional complexity that arises in the testing of hybrid structures at the full scale level occurs due to the fact that the reduction in composite materials performance under hot-wet environmental conditions is normally compensated for by enhancing (increasing) the test loads to be applied at room temperature. This has the affect of overloading the metal structure.

COMPOSITE MATERIAL - SELECTION AND TESTING

As mentioned, the cost of qualifying multiple materials on new aerospace projects is prohibitive and the approach on the Explorer was to choose a single resin system to be used in conjunction with several reinforcing materials from a single supplier. The resin selected was Hexcel's F584 epoxy resin available as a prepreg with T650 3k plain weave carbon and carbon tape, Kevlar 149, and 108, 120 and 181 style glass fiber.

The choice was based on cost and impact resistance (although damage tolerance rather than resistance turned out to be the key design parameter). While F584 is not strictly a toughened material, it does behave in a relatively non-brittle manner and gave significantly better impact resistance than the first generation materials in use at HDH on other programs at the time. A fully toughened system then being used on the Beechcraft Starship was considered but rejected due to its high cost.

Initially 250 °F oven curing systems were considered. However, the lower glass transition temperatures and consequently lower hot-wet properties together with the need to secondarily bond - also at 250°F - mitigated against their selection.

Also in its favor the F584 material has good tack and flow properties that help in processing. An additional factor in the selection was that the material was being considered by McDonnell Douglas Long Beach for the MD12 and subsequently qualified for the MD11. Significant cooperation was provided by Hexcel to the extent of their assisting with the provision of materials and manufacture of test coupons as well as technical support.

The specification written required that the material achieve defined mechanical properties at room temperature, cold-dry and hot-wet conditions. This was somewhat unusual in 1989 but is standard practice today. To qualify the specification, three batches of material were used to manufacture coupons (at MDHS, Hexcel and HDH). Tests were designed to sufficiently characterize the material such that should an alternative be introduced during production, then only these tests would require repeating rather than all the subsequent coupon and component testing. Material Qualification tests were performed on laminate specimens, the former to fix the elastic constants and the latter to provide initial failure strains. This testing gave early warning that the compression after impact property would be the minimum design value.

Design allowables testing was subsequently carried out also by both companies. MDHS carried out coupon testing using the angle minus loaded ply (AML) approach while HDH tested design specific laminates. Table 1 shows the total amount of coupon testing conducted for both material qualification and design allowables. Much of the HDH testing was concerned with the effect of manufacturing flaws in the laminates. This was necessary in order to validate the Non-Destructive Inspection (NDI) acceptance criteria. The flaws were simulated with teflon inserts placed in the laminate during fabrication. Discs of various diameters representing flaws both above and below the threshold of detectability were located in the critical test section of each coupon.

Location	Material	Test Type	Number of Specimens
MDHS	Carbon/Epoxy	Qualification Static	666
	Aramid/Epoxy	Qualification Static	222
	Repair Resin	Qualification Static	251
	Syntactic Foam	Qualification Static	21
	Adhesive Creep	Qualification Static	54
	Carbon/Epoxy	Allowables Static & Fatigue	1170
	Carbon/Epoxy	Qualification Static	612
HDH	Aramid/Epoxy	Qualification Static	195
	Carbon/Epoxy	Allowables Static & Fatigue	719
	Film Adhesive	Allowables Static	95
	Paste Adhesive	Allowables Static	96
	Fasteners	Allowables Static	22
		TOTAL	4123

Table 1 Composite Coupon Tests

The conclusions from the design allowables testing were as follows: From the static tests on the solid laminates at HDH the central hole specimens were more critical than either the central or the edge-flawed specimens at Room Temperature Dry (RTD) conditions. However, the open edge flaws were more critical after exposure to elevated temperature and moisture.

The knockdown factor for the central hole stress raiser was around 40% and 50% while the knockdown factor for environmental soaking was between 25% and 50%. The testing showed that the worst case B Base design value was greater than the initial design value chosen from the results of the laminate tests under the Material Qualification Program. When compared with the (AML) data generated at MDHS for open hole specimens the HDH point

design laminate had higher average and B Base reduced values. From the cyclic fatigue tests at HDH: At Room Temperature / Ambient (RTA) (ambient temperature and humidity), the endurance limit of the (flawed) specimens was greater than 60% of the ultimate failure load (which in turn was greater than the design value strain, see above). At elevated temperature Hot Temperature Wet (HTW) the endurance limit was more than 30% greater than the design limit strain. All cycle testing was carried out with a load range $R=0.5$.

From the testing on sandwich panels, it was shown that static failure strains were again higher than the design values and the fatigue is not a design consideration for this construction. Similarly comforting results were obtained from the testing of joints in which the composite elements consistently outperformed the metallic elements. In support of the Design Allowables testing described above, a number of detail design elements were tested in order to confirm that design values from coupon testing could be applied to component details. This included compression testing of stiffener sections, impact testing of sandwiched and stiffened panels, shear and compression testing on stiffened panels in damaged state and after repair, and fastener tests in composite laminates. The last mentioned was performed in answer to questions raised on the use of locked spindle blind fasteners in composite material. The small head and tail profiles were thought likely to pull through under loading. However, this was not found by the testing.

Since carbon is only a moderate conductor of electricity there is a need to provide shielding against both lightning strike and radio magnetic interference to on-board avionics equipment. This was affected by an expanded aluminum mesh co-cured over the outer carbon fiber ply of the tub and aft fuselage sections. The same protection system was employed at MDHS for the main rotor blades, pitchcase, tailboom and empennage assemblies. Testing was conducted at Lightning Technologies Inc. in the USA on panels fabricated by HDH. The results showed that lightning damage was less catastrophic to the (protected) composite surface than to similar gage aluminum alloy sheet.

The majority of the full scale testing was carried out at MDHS. HDH carried out a number of static and fatigue tests on representative sections and joints within the fuselage and also on the cabin floor. Three full scale fuselages were delivered to MDHS for structural testing two for static tests (pre-production and production versions) and one for fatigue. In addition a number of roof structures were provided; four of these were fatigue tested while one was used for static testing.

CONCLUSIONS

The test program was highly successful and validated a conservative but still light weight design. Only two small beef-up modifications to HDH delivered components were shown necessary by the static testing, only one of these to a composite part. No premature failures have been reported from the fatigue testing.

REFERENCES

1. Christ, Richard A., "Certification Testing of a Hybrid Helicopter Airframe", presented at the American Helicopter Society 52nd Annual Forum, Washington, D.C. June 4-6, 1996.
2. FAA Advisory Circular AC 20-107A, "Composite Aircraft Structure", dated April 25, 1984.

3. Federal Aviation Regulation Part 27, “Airworthiness Standards: Normal Category Rotorcraft, Change 21”, effective April 5, 1995.